

7th E-NEWSLETTER | October 2024

In this last issue for 2024, we are excited to share the latest achievements of the RECONMATIC team! Explore this issue to learn more about our annual meeting in Greece and the Open Day organised in China.

What is clear, at the end of the second year of the project, is that our work results are starting to show. Two project deliverables completed as part of our research on current practices and policies and an Information Management System focused on Material Data flow, led to three new scientific publications as well.

Moreover, the team has achieved the WASTEie Milestone by publishing waste information exchange data set and the European Waste Classification Codes for Construction and Demolition (category 17) on buildingSMART Data Dictionary (bSDD).

Read below all you need to know about our project and clusters' activities and keep an eye on what's coming in the months ahead.

Happy reading!

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RECONMATIC 3rd Annual Meeting: Focus on Innovation, Collaboration and Exploitation

We are excited to share the latest updates from the RECONMATIC 3rd Annual Meeting, where the focus was on innovation, collaboration, and exploitation strategies for advancing our project goals.

[Learn more](#)

RECONMATIC presented in China: 3rd Open Day

The RECONMATIC partners were pleased to host another Open Day focusing on automated solutions for sustainable and circular management of construction and demolition waste (CDW).

[Learn more](#)

Deliverables

RECONMATIC develops a Digital Information Management System focused on Material Data Flow

Insights on Circular Economy Implementation in European Construction #2: The study

This study addresses the construction industry's pivotal role in transitioning to a Circular Economy (CE), despite the industry's inherent resource intensity and

the complex nature of CE implementation.

[Learn more](#)

The RECONMATIC consortium is happy to share the study of the team on the implementation of circular economy principles by the Construction Industry in 5 EU countries and the UK.

[Learn more](#)

Developing WASTEie #3: Celebrating the achievement of the RECONMATIC Milestone!

The RECONMATIC project has made its contribution by developing the WASTEie Data Dictionary together with European Waste Classification codes for construction and demolition, now available on the buildingSMART Data Dictionary (bSDD) platform.

[Learn more](#)

Social Snapshots

Collaboration Decommissioning and Reuse Data Dictionary awarded in the Sustainability Excellence category by buildingSMART International

The RECONMATIC team member, BIMBox, collaborated with Arghavan Akbarieh on the buildingSMART awards submission led by the Eindhoven University of Technology, which was shortlisted in the Professional Research category and selected as a winner in the Sustainability Excellence category.

FEAD
European Waste
Management Association

Conference
**Higher energy
and material
security in EU
countries**

FEAD & CAOoH
International
Conference

31 October 2024,
Prague

ČAOoH
ČESKÁ ASOCIACE OŘEŠOVÉHO HOSPODÁŘSTVÍ

Meet us in the 3rd Annual Conference on Greater Energy and Material Security for EU Countries in Czech Republic

FEAD and **CAOoH**, are organising a conference titled '**Higher energy and material security in EU countries**' and a working seminar in the beautiful city of Prague.

RECONMATIC Open Day in Spain: Discussing Circular Economy in Construction

[Learn more](#)

BLOG

Waste management in the railway field - the Italian case

We explore the **circular engagement** of the Italian railway sector in **Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) management**, highlighting innovative practices aimed at promoting sustainability. By focusing on the reuse and recycling of materials, the Italian railway industry is working to reduce environmental impact while contributing to a circular economy.

[Learn more](#)

RECONMATIC: Addressing the Urgent Need for CDW Management in China

RECONMATIC Innovates the Demolition Waste Management: A BIM-Based System

PUBLICATIONS

In the second year of the RECONMATIC project, our partners at the University of Salford have contributed three significant scientific papers to the field of construction and demolition waste management:

Examining the Challenges for Circular Economy Implementation in Construction and Demolition Waste

Designing for a Circular Economy in the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction Industry: Insights from Italy

A systematic review and meta-analysis of the drivers to support improved construction and demolition waste management for a circular economy

These publications highlight the ongoing research efforts to advance sustainable practices in the built environment.

CLUSTER NEWS & SYNERGIES

Welcoming new members to the Circular Construction Cluster

After joining forces with the **CircularB COST Action**, we are happy to welcome more initiatives joining the Circular Construction Cluster:

- CAMACOL- the **Colombian Chamber of Construction in the Antioquia Region**
- The **Latin American Alliance** for Circular Construction
- The **REDOL** project

Visit our Circular Construction Cluster Webpage to learn more about the members and our aims. Follow [#CircularConstructionCluster](#) and stay tuned for more updates on our growing synergies.

[Learn more](#)

Follow the [#Tech4EUConstruction](#) hashtag to get updates about the activities of the [Tech4EUConstruction Cluster](#).

Some highlights from the last months are the [InCube Webinar 'Empowering Social Inclusion in Construction'](#) and the workshops organised by the cluster members in the **Sustainable Places 2024**.

EVENTS

RECONMATIC's Active Role in CircularB COST Action Meeting at ITÜ

Project presentation in the 88th Thessaloniki International Fair

RECONMATIC at the Net-Zero Future Conference

Upcoming Activities

In the end of October, RECONMATIC is going to be presented in two important industry events.

On the 30th of October, Juan Ferriz-Papi is presenting RECONMATIC developments in the **UKGBC Circular Economy Forum** and on the 31st of October, our project coordinator Jan Valentin is going to participate in the **3rd FEAD – ČAOBH Annual Conference: Greater Energy and Material Security for the Countries of the EU** presenting the RECONMATIC project.

Meanwhile the team is intensively working on completing the tools' development and organising a series of Open Day Events in Spain, Greece and China, during the Spring 2025.

[Contact us](#) if you are interested in joining us and participating in the events and stay tuned via the project's social media channels on LinkedIn ([@RECONMATIC](#)) and X

(@reconmatic)!

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